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Hardware-in-the-Loop OCT Operation in a Simulated Ocean Current Environment

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Abstract

Increased interest in renewable energy production has created demand for novel methods of electricity production. Marine hydro kinetic turbines could serve to help meet this growing power demand with a high potential for low-cost power generation for powering island and coastal communities, as well as blue economy industries. The large potential for electricity generation powered by ocean currents has gained attention as a viable renewable energy source that can be harnessed by ocean current turbines (OCTs). In this paper, a 3-HP OCT dynamometer is equipped in a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) executed in the Opal-RT environment. Real-time performance in a simulated ocean environment has been investigated where the ocean flow speed and the ocean turbulence intensity are both varied.

Keywords: Ocean Current Turbine; Hardware-In-Loop; Marine hydrokinetic; Real-time simulator

Nomenclature

Variable Frequency Driver (VFD): A device used to vary frequency and voltage used for an AC induction motor.

Hardware-In-Loop (HIL): A testing method that integrates physical components into a simulated environment to validate and refine system performance.

Ocean Current Turbine (OCT): a renewable energy device that harnesses the kinetic energy of ocean currents to generate electricity.

1.0 Introduction

Marine hydrokinetic (MHK) energy has garnered attention as a promising and stable solution to increase our renewable energy sources. Ocean current turbines (OCTs) have emerged as a viable choice for utility-scale power generation due to the constant, predictable flow of ocean currents. As research in MHK energy and OCT development continues to grow, there is an increasing demand for reliable simulation and testing. This paper aims to explore the potential of real-time simulators and hardware-in-loop (HIL) testing in assessing the functionality and performance of ocean current turbines before their deployment, thereby contributing to safe and efficient renewable energy research and development.

HIL testing offers a crucial advantage by enabling the evaluation of OCTs in realistic virtual environments. The ability to generate a wide range of virtual environments allows for early detection of potential issues and effective risk mitigation, ultimately enhancing the reliability of ocean current turbines. While literature specifically addressing HIL testing for OCTs remains scarce, we can draw from related wind turbine studies due to the similarities between the two technologies. For instance, [1] demonstrates the use of a HIL setup to investigate active power control methods and low-voltage ride-through in wind turbines. Existing research on MHK technology includes HIL testing for an

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OCT [4], tidal turbine [5], and oscillating water column [6]. Despite the potential of HIL testing for OCTs, the literature regarding its application and effectiveness in this specific context is sparse. This study aims to contribute to the knowledge base of HIL testing for MHK devices and help bridge the gap in this research.

2.0 Hardware-in-loop Integration

This project utilizes the Opal-RT 4510 as the main device for real-time simulation in this system, which is controlled from the host computer and uses Simulink models to create environments that can interact with external devices in real time. The OCT Simulink model used creates ocean current fluctuations to send input signals to the variable frequency drive (VFD) which controls the shaft torque into the motor to mimic OCT operations in a realistic ocean environment. The analog and digital input signals are transmitted from the simulator to the VFD of the driving motor, with analog signals setting the speed reference and digital signals controlling the run of the motor (Figure 1). The driving motor VFD is therefore what controls the motor under test (MUT), since the two are mechanically coupled forming a 3HP dynamometer via a torque cell. The MUT features a dual channel encoder that is connected to the simulator. This provides real-time speed feedback signals and enables seamless integration of motor RPM data back into the Simulink model. This closed HIL configuration allows comprehensive testing of the MUT under varied conditions while maintaining precise feedback accuracy. Furthermore, the Opal-RT's interpretation of encoder signals accurately determines dynamometer speed and position, enabling the integration of a simulated OCT model with the physical MUT.

Figure 1: Hardware-in-loop setup for Opal-RT.

When simulating ocean currents, it is important to factor in parameters such as rotor depth, rotor diameter, significant wave height, turbulence intensity, and current flow speed. Accounting for these parameters, a simplified model can be produced that accurately simulates a realistic OCT in an ocean current environment using calculations based on [6], which can be explained using one main equation where the total water velocity, U_{tot} , is calculated by adding the current flow speed, U_f , with the wave-induced water velocity, U_{wave} , and the flow speed turbulence U_{turb} as seen below:

$$U_{tot} = U_f + U_{wave} + U_{turb} \quad (1)$$

The resulting U_{tot} equation is then used as the flow speed input to calculate the mechanical torque on the OCT, which is then converted to RPM in order to match the input parameters of the VFD. This is done using the following equation with RPM as a function of the inertia of the simulated turbine which is calculated in [2], where $I = 539,490 \text{ Nm}^3$, and the mechanical torque (T_m) as seen below:

$$RPM = \int \frac{T_m * 60}{I * 2\pi} \quad (2)$$

The RPM is then scaled by a factor of 10 to match the RPM scaling of the driving motor. This model, as seen in Figure 2, simulates an OCT with realistic ocean current fluctuations that is dependent on the flow speed set by the

user based on the OCT model in [7]. By converting the output mechanical torque of the OCT model to RPM in order to match the driving motor a functional hardware-in-loop system that simulates the ocean environment is created. Figure 2 features the OCT model block along with RT-Lab blocks which enable the model to communicate with external devices and log data.

Figure 2: RT-Lab Simulink master subsystem with OCT Model (Green Subsystem).

3.0 Test Run and Results

The Simulink models are executed in real-time using the RT-Lab software. The Simulink model is controlled via the control subsystem that is seen in Figure 3 where the “Run Forward” switch controls the on and off of the motor, and the rotary switch controls the flow speed of the ocean current to set the OCT model at. This enables control of the HIL system through the host computer and gives the user the ability to adjust the simulated flow speed of the OCT in real-time.

The flow speed input of the OCT model is varied see observe the effects of changing ocean current water velocities affect the power generation of the turbine. As the flow speed increases or decreases the RPM follows and matches the fluctuations as seen in Figure 4. In the Figure the top graph displays the input RPM (red) compared to the RPM feedback from the dynamometer (blue) and the bottom graph shows the flow speed to show when it gets stepped up and stepped down. As seen, the input OCT fluctuations almost directly match the dynamometer feedback RPM which indicates the system is effectively feeling the fluctuations from the OCT model.

Figure 3: RT-Lab Simulink Control Console Subsystem.

The OpWriteFile block is utilized to log crucial data including RPM input, RPM feedback, flow speed, and time. This data is depicted in Figure 4, which shows a comparative analysis between RPM input and RPM feedback derived from the actual MUT encoder feedback. This analysis sheds light on the dynamic relationship between simulated

ocean current environments and its effects on HIL systems. A direct correlation is evident between the input and feedback RPM values and shows how accurately the motor followed the ocean current fluctuations. Additionally, the second graph shows the variation in flow speed over time. This plot highlights a clear cause-and-effect relationship, demonstrating that heightened flow speed directly corresponds to an increase in the turbines RPM. Noise becomes noticeable at approximately 500 RPM, with prominent spikes occurring around 700 RPM. This occurrence likely stems from various factors. One probable explanation is the influence of resonant frequencies within specific materials. These resonant frequencies could amplify vibrations, leading to distortions in the encoder's readings. To address this issue, implementing shock absorbers or a suspension system could potentially mitigate noise levels at this specific RPM range.

OCT RPM Input and Feedback, Varying Flow Speed

Figure 4: OCT Model HIL Setup Operation Under Varying Flow Speeds; RPM Input, RPM Feedback, & Flow Speed.

The simulated ocean turbulence intensity was varied to observe the motor performance under increasingly turbulent flow speed conditions. Figure 5 below shows the motor operating under the ocean current conditions of 1 m/s current flow speed and 5% (left), 10% (middle), and 15% (right) turbulence intensity, TI , which are considered to be realistic ocean environment characteristics.

OCT RPM Input and Feedback, Varying Turbulence

Figure 5: OCT Model HIL setup operation under varying turbulence intensities; $TI = 5\%$ (left), $TI = 10\%$ (middle), $TI = 15\%$ (right).

4.0 Conclusion

The presented research paper demonstrated a successful HIL simulation of an OCT model utilizing the Opal-RT platform for real-time system integration. This paper underscores the efficiency and reliability of HIL testing for OCTs, and the outcomes showcased the exceptional accuracy of the motor's performance across a spectrum of flow velocities. The OCT model captures the authentic mechanical torque output under specific parameters and simulations distinctly illustrate that the MUT adeptly orchestrates real-time simulations of ocean current fluctuations, especially under increasing turbulent conditions. This exploration illustrates the potential of HIL simulations as an indispensable tool for the precise and reliable testing of OCT equipment prior to deployment. By harnessing this methodology, critical objectives such as risk mitigation, performance validation, grid integration, and expedited control system assessments can be effectively achieved. The implications of this research open new avenues for enhancing the robustness, safety, and efficiency of OCT systems, bolstering their readiness for real-world challenges.

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